

**THE PRIORITY OF HUMAN INTERESTS IN UZBEKISTAN'S
IDEOSPHERIC DEVELOPMENT**

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Annotation: This article is dedicated to explaining the coherence of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals of the principle that human interests are above all else in Uzbekistan. Also, all the Sustainable Development Goals are studied in depth, and the issues of their application to the life of the society are analyzed. This process underscores the important idea that without human progress, societal development cannot occur.

Keywords: development, humanity, ideosphere, equality, strategy, human rights, spirituality, democracy, ecology, society.

On September 25, 2015, leaders from all countries agreed at the “Rio+20” conference to adopt a sustainable development program aimed at addressing various issues related to poverty, inequality, and climate change, with a target period up to 2030. Subsequently, with the aim of moving from these requirements to concrete actions, the new development program was officially adopted at the historic UN summit in New York in September 2015, where the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [1] were endorsed [2].

The Sustainable Development Goals 2030 program consists of 17 new Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), or global goals. It serves as a framework for global policies and investment directions over the next 15 years. It envisions the complete eradication of poverty in all its forms and everywhere across the world [3]. All of this aims to implement the 17 Sustainable Development Goals and 169 tasks arising from them, which must be achieved by 2030 [4].

The new 17 Sustainable Development Goals of the Sustainable Development 2030 Program:

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

The above global goals, aimed at serving the advancement of all humanity, envision the complete eradication of poverty on Earth, achieving full gender equality, advancing healthcare to a new level of quality, ensuring every child has access to education, and directing the world towards sustainable development. These goals are expected to find their solutions by 2030 and are highly anticipated to contribute significantly to human advancement. Our country is not excluded from these global processes. In particular, on September 25, 2015, Uzbekistan joined the international agreement “Sustainable Development Goals” together with 193 countries of the world [5]. Today, the state policy implemented in the field of human development in the spiritual renewal of Uzbekistan corresponds to these goals and is recognized by foreign experts. The goals of the Actions strategy are in line with the UN Sustainable Development Goals. In the new phase of Uzbekistan’s development, the draft concept of advancing the national idea includes a key objective of integrating Uzbekistan into the group of the 50 most developed democratic countries by 2030. This aligns with the Sustainable Development Goals and demonstrates its democratic relevance [6]. After all, these goals open the door to the development of our country and its growth, and ensure the well-being of the people and the stability of our country.

In our country, the State programs being adopted in accordance with the Actions Strategy aligned with the UN Sustainable Development Goals, as well as the laws and other regulatory documents derived from them, serve the well-being of individuals. It is no coincidence that President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized in his speech at the ceremony dedicated to the 25th anniversary of

the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan that “our efforts to ensure human rights are fully aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals” [7]. From this perspective, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 21, 2018, on “Approval of the Strategy for Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2021” [8], the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated October 20, 2018, on “Measures for Implementing National Goals and Objectives in the Field of Sustainable Development up to 2030” [9], and the joint decision of the Legislative Chamber and Senate of the Oliy Majlis dated February 27, 2020, on “Formation of a Parliamentary Commission to Monitor the Implementation of National Goals and Objectives in the Field of Sustainable Development up to 2030” [10] are important strategic reforms confirming the alignment of our country’s goals with the extensive objectives outlined above for the year 2030.

On the basis of these documents, the national goals and tasks in the field of sustainable development until 2030 have been approved, and the Coordinating Council has been established in Uzbekistan for their implementation and is carrying out its activities. Moreover, today, specialists from the operational UN offices in our country also emphasize that this program holds significant importance as a criterion for human advancement in the process of our nation’s spiritual renewal. The UN Sustainable Development Goals concept is aimed at achieving objectives that encompass the interrelated aspects of human well-being, considering global human needs, and focuses on shaping a lifestyle that integrates human health, literacy levels, ecological safety, economic prosperity, social protection, and institutional cohesion.

In short, the greatest wealth of our country is the human factor. In the implementation of this, at the heart of the large-scale strategic reforms carried out by our state is the goal of raising the standard of living of the population, ensuring the comfortable life of every citizen, and creating all the conditions for their happy living. In this regard, the successful implementation of a number of important strategic measures for the future guarantees that Uzbekistan will rise to the target level in the human development index.

References:

1. About the Sustainable Development Goals // <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-development-goals/>
2. New Sustainable Development Program // <https://www.uz.undp.org/content/uzbekistan/uz/home/post-2015.html>
3. Sustainable Development Goals // <http://www.un.uz/ozb/pages/display/sdgs>

4. Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development //Resolution adopted by the General Assembly on 25 September 2015.
5. Saidova L. Fulfillment of sustainable development goals and prospects of the education sector in Uzbekistan //Democratization and human rights, No. 1, 2018. -p.19.
6. Concept of development of a national idea at a new stage of development of Uzbekistan // <https://regulation.gov.uz/uz/document/10558>
7. Mirziyoev Sh.M. The Constitution is a solid foundation for our free and prosperous life, further development of our country // "Khalk sozi" newspaper, December 8, 2017. №247 (6941).
8. Decree No. PF-5544 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 21, 2018 "On approval of the innovative development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2021" // <https://www.lex.uz/en/>
9. Resolution No. 841 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 20, 2018 "On measures to implement national goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development until 2030" // <https://www.lex.uz/en/>
10. The joint decision of the Council of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Council of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 27, 2020 "On establishing a parliamentary commission to monitor the implementation of national goals and tasks in the field of sustainable development of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" // <https://www.lex.uz/en/>
11. Sobirovich, T. B. (2020). The criterion of human indicators in development and renewals in Uzbekistan. EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR), 6(8), 509-511.
12. Sobirovich, T. B. (2021). The implementation of human indicator reforms in Uzbekistan. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research, 10(9), 197-202.
13. Sobirovich, T. B. (2023). Basic Criteria for Building the Third Renaissance in Uzbekistan. Asian Journal of Applied Science and Technology (AJAST), 7(1), 149-157.
14. Sobirovich, T. B. (2022). A study of national and universal principles of democracy. Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities, 12(5), 417-421.
15. Sobirovich, T. B. National Revival and Development Idiosphere of Uzbekistan.-2023. In International scientific-online conference International scientific-online conference.

